

DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN EFL CLASSES

Hushnoza Abduvohidova

EFL Teacher of Namangan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7138957>

Abstract: Communicative competence is a complex, multi-stage process that includes the developing of each of its components, which include the development of a whole range of skills. All components of communicative competence are interconnected, and we discuss on the development of one or another sub-competence in a particular situation in this article.

Key words: communicative competence, component, function, technique, development, English classes

Аннотация: Коммуникативная компетентность представляет собой сложный, многоэтапный процесс, включающий развитие каждого из ее компонентов, включающих в себя развитие целого комплекса умений и навыков. Все компоненты коммуникативной компетенции взаимосвязаны, и в данной статье речь пойдет о развитии той или иной субкомпетенции в конкретной ситуации.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативная компетентность, компонент, функция, методика, развитие, занятия английским языком.

Communicative competence is perceived as a person's ability to understand and generate foreign language statements in various socially determined situations, taking into account the linguistic and social rules in target language.

According to the research of the Council of Europe, J. Van Ek identified the following components of communicative competence in 1975:

1) Linguistic competence (knowledge of phonetic, lexical and grammatical material);

2) Sociolinguistic competence (correspondence of statements to a certain situation of communication, taking into account its formal or informal nature);

3) Sociocultural competence (knowledge of the sociocultural context);

4) Social competence (desire and willingness to interact with other people in a foreign language);

5) Discursive competence (the ability to understand and generate coherent speech statements);

6) Strategic competence (the ability to compensate for the lack of knowledge by means of language, speech and social experience of communication) (Van Ek, 1990).

The functions of communicative competence can be distinguished:

- Function of information and communicative is manifested in the processes of transmission and reception of information by interlocutors;
- The regulatory and control function is revealed in influencing the behavior of partners in the process of communication;
- Emotional-communicative function affects the emotional state of the interlocutor.

When we plan each lesson, it is necessary to proceed from the main methodological bases of teaching a foreign language. The following teaching aids are an important condition for organizing the successful development of communicative competence in a foreign language classes:

1) The textbook is the main learning tool. It contains material on teaching all types of speech activity (listening, speaking, reading, and writing);

2) A workbook is important for independent work and allows you to assimilate lexical and grammatical material, reinforcing it by completing assignments for each lesson. In addition, the workbook develops self-control;

3) Diagrams, tables, illustrations, handouts make it possible to activate the formation and development of all types of speech activity, and also contribute to the accumulation of units of language and speech in memory;

4) Book to develop reading skills in English. Additional texts play a positive role in achieving educational, developmental and educational goals;

5) Teaching aids for independent work, research work;

6) Audio and video materials play a very important role in learning English. They reproduce the speech of native speakers; students improve the quality of pronunciation, and develop the ability to understand speech by ear;

7) Computer programs and the internet provide opportunity to study independently or remotely. The Internet is especially effective for developing writing skills;

Since communicative competence is developed through speech interaction, we need to consider:

1) cooperation (used to develop a single idea, with the help of which a problematic problem is solved);

2) combination (when initially different participants have different information, communicate with each other and an exchange occurs between them);

3) execution of the instruction (one participant of speech interaction transmits information to another).

We can assign such tasks to develop communicative competence of students.

- communicative games;
 - picture gap - students are given almost identical pictures, differences must be found using questions without seeing the picture of another student;
 - text gap (jigsaw reading) - students have similar texts or fragments of the same text, information from one student is missing in the text of another student, and this gap needs to be filled;
 - knowledge gap (complete-the-table tasks) - one student has data that another does not have, and they need to be entered into the table;
 - belief gap - students share different opinions, develop cognitive skills;
 - reasoning gap - students have different evidence, and they need to be brought together and compared.
 - communicative simulations in role-plays and problem-solving (communicative simulations);
 - role-playing games (a certain set of characters and a game problem situation are required in which these characters act. The behavior of the participants is built depending on the behavior of each other, as well as their communicative goal. The resolution of the conflict becomes the result of the game).
 - Round tables - taking part in the round table, the student expresses his opinion. Problems or questions for discussion can be different: regional studies, social, moral and ethical. In order for schoolchildren to be able to participate in the round table, they must have a sufficiently high level of language proficiency, as well as sufficient knowledge on the issue of discussion).
- In short, we need create communicative situations with the help of abovementioned tasks so that students interact, develop the ability to think critically in English lessons.

References:

1. Van Ek J. A. Waystage 1990: Council of Europe. Cambridge University Press.
2. Vahid, N. L. (2011). Learners' communicative competence in English as a foreign language (EFL). *International Journal of English and Literature*, 2(7), 161-165.
3. Sarimsakova, D. (2019). COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AS A RESULT OF EF TEACHING AND LEARNING. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (12), 166-169.
4. Alimova, M. H. (2021). Defining the differences between genders in foreign language learning strategies. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 464-467.